

Mobility and the reuse of Roman Roads for the deposition of Viking Age silver hoards in North West England

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Abstract

Discussions on Viking Age silver hoards in North West England have been dominated by analysis of the material compositions of the hoards. Despite a multi-century research legacy concerning the material composition of the Viking Age silver hoards, the relationship of the hoards to their transport and depositional locations has been understudied. The relationship of the hoards to early medieval overland transport links is studied in this paper with an optimal pathways modelling process in a Geographic Information System (GIS). The modelling process incorporates multiple cost of vertical movement functions to simulate human agency when moving through the landscape, error inherent in the Digital Elevation Model creation process, and preferential movement on re-used Romano-British roads. As a result of this analysis, it is suggested that the median travel time from early medieval period routeways to the hoard deposition points is 16 minutes. Over half of the hoards may have been placed under 25 minutes' walk from the routeways. This finding supports an interpretation that the hoards are concealed deposits intended for retrieval, rather than ritual deposits that were not intended for retrieval.

Introduction

There are 18 Viking Age (c. AD 790-1000) silver hoards known in England's North West (*figure 1*), the historic counties of Cheshire, Lancashire, Cumberland, and Westmorland. These silver hoards are temporally concentrated in the tenth century, are of Viking-Age Scandinavian economic character, and demonstrate material wealth accrued from a far-reaching Viking Age communication network (Kershaw 2017*b*). The silver discovered in the North West ranges in provenance from as near as the Scandinavian-controlled Northumbrian Kingdom in York and as far away as the Middle East (Graham-Campbell 2011, Kershaw 2017*b*, Kershaw *et al.* 2021). The Scandinavian-character material components of the hoards include silver bullion ('hack silver'), Anglo-Saxon and Anglo-Scandinavian coinage, ornaments of ninth century Irish Sea type, and ninth to tenth century Arabic coins, known as dirhams.

There was an apparent substantial exchange of silver across the Pennines in the Viking Age. Geographically, the North West sits between the Pennines – the largest range of hills in England – and the Irish Sea. The North West is historically considered the middle point between the 'linked Viking kingdoms' of York and Dublin (Graham-Campbell 2011). Communication routes between the two would have traversed both the Pennines and the Irish Sea (Edmonds 2020, Horne 2021). York origin, or Anglo-Scandinavian, numismatic components are frequently found deposited in Scandinavian economic character hoards alongside metalwork of the Irish Sea, or Hiberno-Norse, region (Graham-Campbell 2011,

Williams 2011, Edmonds 2020). The apparent exchange of metalwork across the Pennines coincided with the southern Scandinavian control of and alliance between the 'linked' kingdoms in York and Dublin, broadly during the late ninth century to mid-tenth century, and the Scandinavian settlement in the North West during the tenth and early eleventh centuries (*cf.* Williams 2009, Higham 2004).

Alongside strong implications of the flow of metalwork across the Pennines, recent investigations into the early medieval routeways and communications systems in the North West have yielded a list of known tenth century transport nodes (Edmonds 2020) that are presumed to have been in use at a contemporary date to the deposition of the silver hoards. Specifically, communications systems formed from the framework of the remaining Romano-British road network (*figure 2*) may have facilitated the exchange of silver across the Pennines between York and Dublin (Williams 2009, Graham-Campbell 2011, Kershaw 2017*b*). The remnants of the Romano-British road network may have been maintained in the early medieval period for efficient overland transport across the Pennines (Edmonds 2020). Despite the knowledge that the cross-Pennine communications network existed in part on re-used Romano-British roads where available, the specific courses of early medieval period routes are not known. The uncertainty in routeway positioning is due to the fragmentary nature of current knowledge on Romano-British road courses and the possibility that previously-unmentioned transport nodes exist.

It is intended that this paper will help resolve questions as to the ritual or functional character of the hoards (Graham-Campbell 1992, 2011; Raffield 2014; Bradley 2017). Central to these debates is the relationship of the hoards to early medieval routes – if the hoards were non-ritual and intended for retrieval, they would be concealed from high-traffic areas of the landscape, but close enough to high-traffic areas to be easily recovered by those with knowledge of their location. There are two principal questions that are explored in this paper. The first of these is 'how do the hoards with known locations relate to early medieval period routeways leading away from York?' The second of these questions is 'can the hoards' relationships with cross-Pennine routeways be interpreted as a means for concealment away from the routeways'? To answer these questions, a bespoke Geographic Information Systems (GIS) modelling process was developed in ArcGIS Pro 3.0 and Jupyter notebooks. This process uses a Least Cost Pathways (LCP) methodology that takes into account human agency realized with multiple cost of movement functions, random errors inherent in the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) creation process, the visualization of uncertainty in LCP modelling using rasterized line densities, and recently re-discovered fragments of Roman Road that have been observed in the last decade via Remote Sensing methods and archaeological excavation (Ratledge 2023).

Figure 1 – Viking Age silver hoards in North West England. Multiple hoards are located in close proximity (under one kilometer) in Flusco Pike (2) and Chester (2). The ‘Lancashire’ Hoard, reported by antiquarian Beaupré Bell in 1734 (*cf.* Blunt and Stewart 1983), does not have precise coordinates due the ambiguous reporting of its discovery in the eighteenth century, and is therefore not depicted on the map.

Figure 2 – The Romano-British road network from the 1st-4th century AD, the framework of the reused medieval road network. Earlier knowledge of Roman Roads in black dash (McCormick *et al.* 2013) are displayed against Ratledge’s (2023) newly-discovered courses in solid red and Early Medieval period transport nodes (*cf.* Edmonds, 2020). With special thanks to David Ratledge for advice on road courses in this figure.

Background

Northern England and the ‘Southern Scandinavian’ Economy

In the mid-ninth century to eleventh century, Ireland and Central Britain were participants in a Southern Scandinavian economic sphere (*figure 3*), part of which was driven by the exchange of silver (Horne 2021). Britain was forcibly brought into the southern Scandinavian economy in c. AD 866 by members of the *Uí Ímair* dynasty (Downham 2007, Nebolini 2020, Horne 2021), who were also in control of Dublin. In the opinion of Horne (2021), Scandinavian agents were intent on establishing a ‘market polity’ in Britain and Ireland that was able to link with the Scandinavian economic arena already in operation in Northern Europe and the Baltic during the ninth century. Various forms of silver numismatic economy existed in Anglo-Saxon England from the seventh century (Kershaw 2017*a*), although the Scandinavian expansion into Britain and Ireland was likely motivated by the availability in Britain of other elements of the Scandinavian economy. Trading routes, natural resources, arable land, commodities, and slaves were all important elements of the Scandinavian economy (*cf.* Graham-Campbell 2011, Sindbæk 2013, Kershaw 2017*a*, Horne 2021) that were present in Northern England in the ninth century.

Furthermore, and perhaps most importantly, Britain represented a barrier to movement between Scandinavian-controlled Dublin and the North Sea. North West England has previously been pointed to as the midpoint between the linked kingdoms of York and Dublin (Graham-Campbell 2011). However, Horne (2021) expanded this thesis and stated that Northern England is the midpoint between

Scandinavian-controlled Dublin and Southern Scandinavian markets around the North Sea and Baltic (see *figure 3*). Northern England was effectively a land barrier in a maritime-based trade network, and was therefore highly significant as a strategic crossing point. Horne (2021) built on Gooch's (2012) explanation that the North West was the fastest crossing point of the Pennines, England's largest range of hills. This land crossing was the fastest link to the North Sea, compared with sailing around Scotland (Edmonds 2020, Horne 2021). Crossing was facilitated by the Romano-British road network in North West England. These roads (*figures 4 and 5*) were the 'path of least resistance' between Ireland and Southern Scandinavia, a phenomenon dubbed by Horne as the 'Cuerdale corridor' (2021). The capture of York in 866 therefore eliminated the barrier to the path of least geographical resistance for the distribution of economic assets between Scandinavian-controlled Ireland and markets of Southern Scandinavian and Northern Europe.

After Britain was brought into the Scandinavian economic zone, the trade of silver forms compatible with the Scandinavian economy was introduced. A silver Anglo-Scandinavian coinage was established in the mid-late ninth century (Blackburn 2004). However, vast quantities of bullion silver were imported to Southern Scandinavia from the Arabic world in the ninth and tenth centuries in the form of *Dirham* coins (Graham-Campbell 2011, Kershaw 2017*a,b*, Horne 2021). Additionally, many silver ornaments from Ireland were common imports into Britain and Scandinavia and were valued according to their display value or as bullion (Graham-Campbell 2011). Despite having silver Anglo-Scandinavian coinage, ornament and bullion silver was important in England in the ninth and tenth centuries as it was a mutable form of silver that could be universally traded within the Scandinavian economy on the basis of weight. It has been shown through an analysis of single finds of silver bullion and cubo-octohedral weights used to weigh silver bullion that bullion was actively used in the Danelaw alongside numismatic silver and was traded according to set weight units (Kershaw 2017*a*). The use of bullion alongside official coinage can be interpreted as a method of both exchange with diverse forms of economy and a retainer of southern Scandinavian identity (Kershaw 2017*a*). These silver economic uses all play a part in the observed composition of Viking Age silver hoards found in North West England, which will be discussed below.

Figure 3 – The Southern Scandinavian economic zone (Horne 2021, 13, fig. 1.2), including the “Cuerdale Corridor” across the Pennines. Image © Tom Horne 2021, reproduced with kind permission.

Figure 4 – Vestiges of the Romano-British road at Kiln Trees Lane, near Cabus, Lancashire. The bank and agger has been worn down in centuries of usage (Ratledge, 2023). Image © David Ratledge, reproduced with kind permission.

Figure 5 – An extant bank and agger earthwork at Downham (Lancashire) associated with the Ribchester to York route. Image © David Ratledge, reproduced with kind permission.

Hoard Composition

The composition of Scandinavian-character silver hoards in North West England (*table 1*) illustrate different methods of exchange in the Southern Scandinavian economy and fall into three categories. These are:

- 1) Ornamental hoards that contain complete silver ornaments traded by display value,
- 2) Bullion/hack-silver hoards that contain silver (including coins) traded by weight value,
- 3) Mixed bullion hoards that contain both ornaments and hack-silver.

The 42.6 kilogram mixed-category Cuerdale Hoard (Lancashire) dates from approximately AD 905-910 and contained a broad range of silver pieces in a lead container, with many silver ornaments, bullion pieces, and a strong coin component of around 7,500 coins. Many of the coins deposited in the Cuerdale Hoard were freshly-minted in York preceding its deposition (Archibald 1992, Graham-Campbell 2011, Williams 2020). Debates on the assembly point of the Cuerdale Hoard have been prevalent in its historiography. It has been suggested that the hoard was assembled in Ireland (Graham-Campbell 1992, 2011), and other authors have suggested that the hoard could have been assembled in York (Williams 2011, Horne 2021). Given the freshly-minted York coin and the availability of the Irish-origin components across central Britain in other Viking hoards, it is likely that the hoard was assembled in York or nearer its deposition point in Lancashire. The mixed-category Silverdale Hoard (Lancashire) (*figure 6*) dates from around AD 910 and is largely of similar composition to the Cuerdale Hoard, although its weight substantially smaller than Cuerdale at roughly 1 kilogram. The Silverdale Hoard features several particularly remarkable broad-band and pennannular arm rings, comparable to those found at Cuerdale and the Hare Island Hoard in Ireland (Broughton 2011). The Silverdale Hoard also featured numerous ingots and bullion, around 20 coins, and fragments of a lead container (*Ibid.*). One of the coins from Silverdale is a likely Northumbrian issue and references a previously-unknown Norse-Northumbrian ruler 'Iredeconvt' or 'Harthacnut' (*Ibid.*). The bullion-category Huxley Hoard (Cheshire) (*figure 7*) contained numerous bullion pieces including flattened bracelets, a piece of hacked bracelet, an ingot, and fragments of a lead box (Oakden 2014). The other hoards in North West England did not include archaeological evidence for containers, but could have feasibly included organic containers them due to soil preservation conditions (*cf.* Gruszczynski 2017).

Figure 6 – The Silverdale Hoard. Image © The Portable Antiquities Scheme, reproduced under the CC BY-SA 4.0 license.

Figure 7 – The Huxley Hoard. Image © National Museums Liverpool, reproduced under the CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 license.

	Name	County	Category	Deposition Date Range (AD)	Container
1	Cuerdale	Lancashire	Mixed	905-910	Lead
2	Huxley	Cheshire	Bullion	900-910	Lead
3	Silverdale	Lancashire	Mixed	900-910	Lead
4	Harkirk	Lancashire	Mixed	910-915	
5	Dean	Cumbria	Coin	915-925	Lead
6	Lancashire	Lancashire	Coin	910-920	
7	Chester (St. John)	Cheshire	Coin	915-920	
8	Warton/Carnforth	Lancashire	Mixed	920-929	
9	Flusco Pike (2)	Cumbria	Mixed	920-929	
10	Scotby	Cumbria	Mixed	935-940	
11	Flusco Pike (1)	Cumbria	Ornament	920-939	
12	Orton Scar	Cumbria	Ornament		
13	Eccleston	Cheshire	Bullion		
14	Barrow-in-Furness	Cumbria	Mixed	900-930	
15	Chester (Castle Esplanade)	Cheshire	Mixed	965-970	Pot
16	Halton Moor	Lancashire	Mixed	1025-1030	Silver Cup
17	West Coast Cumbria	Cumbria	Mixed	850-950	
18	Furness	Cumbria	Mixed	955-957	

Table 1 – Viking Age silver hoards with their material composition and container types.

Concealed vs Ritual Deposits

Bradley (2017) alluded to two strands of thought concerning hoarded or votive deposits: one relating to the study of the artefact assemblage and another relating to the landscape environment of the

deposit. Bradley claimed that hoarded artefacts had been ‘studied to exhaustion’, whereas the study of the landscape context of hoards would yield more fruitful results, particularly at multiple spatio-temporal scales. Speaking purely of artefactual composition, assemblages are often considered ritual or votive in character if there is a physical quality of the assemblage that demonstrates it is not intended for retrieval. This may be because the deposit contains artefacts that are deliberately broken or non-functional in their normal purpose (Raffield 2014, Bradley 2017). Another indicator of votive deposition is that an assemblage is not enclosed in a container, implying that the depositor is not concerned with keeping its contents assembled for a later date (Gruszczynski 2017). On the other hand, whole or functional artefacts may be considered non-ritual and intended for retrieval (Bradley 2017) or artefacts that are deposited in containers can indicate intent for retrieval (Gruszczynski 2017). It is acknowledged that containers are often made of organic components and are prone to decomposition in certain soil conditions, rendering them archaeologically invisible (*Ibid.*). However, the lack of a container can be inferred where artefacts of different temporal scales and type have been continually deposited at a site, such as the continual prehistoric to Scandinavian Iron Age assemblages from Vimose, Denmark (Jensen 2009) or the Viking Age metalwork found near London Bridge (Wilson 1965).

A more granular understanding of hoarding and its relationship to votive deposition can be gained from the study of the landscape in which assemblages are deposited, than can be gained from the study of artefacts alone. Context is often key to interpreting the way in which sites and assemblages relate to one another, by adding a spatio-temporal dimension to their interpretation. Bradley (2017) illustrates that watercourses and bogs have been shown to be consistent attractors for votive deposition over the *longue durée*, particularly in Scandinavia from the Bronze Age to the post-Roman Iron Age. Raffield (2014) illustrated that in Viking Age England, votive deposition of weaponry was often concentrated at bogs or watercourses, particularly in wetlands around the Thames and the vast wetlands of the Fens. An important finding of Raffield’s study is that Viking Age weaponry deposited in irretrievable environments in England, such as Fens, could be both broken or whole. In fact, whole pre-depositional alteration of weapons was only securely observed in four of 70 examples presented in Raffield’s 2014 paper. This has significant implications for the understanding of Viking Age votive deposition in England – votive deposits need not be broken or non-functional in order to be considered votive, they simply need to be placed in an irretrievable location. Building on this thesis, Raffield (2014) postulated that the landscapes of Viking Age silver hoards in England were potentially deposited in votive locations – the Harkirk, Silverdale, and Carnforth hoards were deposited near windblown sand beaches that had a potentially cosmological implication in the minds of their depositors, and the Cuerdale Hoard was deposited near a fording point on the banks of the River Ribble. However, Raffield does imply that the understanding of the landscape of votive deposition in England is hindered by the lack of understanding of Early Medieval routeways (2014) and hints that routes may also play a part in the landscape setting of hoards. Furthermore, the extent of wetland areas in Early Medieval period England is unknown and highly-conjectural at the local scale (*cf.* Bradley 2017,23; Stein 2014), except where large-scale post-medieval dyking has drained large, historically-attested former wetland basins, such as in the Fens, Holderness, or Morecambe Bay lowlands. Finally, the need for the assessment of the artefacts in conjunction with landscape is illustrated with Raffield’s (2014) study, particularly where silver hoards in North West England are concerned. The silver hoards were of considerable current economic value when they were deposited: although some objects, such as coins, brooches, and ingots were hacked with a type of chisel before deposition, this is due to the objects being actively used as bullion. The range of cultural connections, political prowess, commodity exchange, and physical force that helped assemble silver hoards in North West England must have been considerable and contributed to their current value at the point of deposition.

Materials and Methodology

Two principal methodological steps are key to address the research questions that drive this paper. The first of these is the creation of a suite of probabilistic LCPs displayed as line densities to describe movement between early medieval period transport nodes derived from Edmonds (2020) (*table 2*). The second of these is the depiction of optimal paths line densities leading from the points of highest-density travel near the hoard locations to the hoard’s depositional points. The GIS modelling process was

implemented using ArcGIS Pro 3.0 geoprocessing tools within a Jupyter notebook (supplied in this article’s supplemental material page at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11067607>).

Origin	Destination
York	Knaresborough, Tadcaster
Knaresborough	Broughbridge, Tadcaster
Broughbridge	Richmond, Ilkley
Tadcaster	Manchester, Doncaster, Ilkley
Ilkley	Manchester, Bainbridge, Ingleton, Elslack
Ribchester	Preston
Clitheroe	Elslack, Ribchester
Walton-le-Dale	Preston, Wigan
Manchester	Wigan, Stockport, Northwich, Carlisle
Chester	Northwich, Runcorn, Meols, Repton, Dore
Lancaster	Ribchester, Preston, Carnforth, Ingleton
Kendal	Carnforth, Ingleton, Bainbridge, Ravenglass, Barrow
Doncaster	Dore
Bainbridge	Richmond, Ingleton
Carnforth	Barrow
Brough	Richmond, Penrith
Ravenglass	Carlisle
Preston	Kirkham, Ribchester

Table 2 – Major route pairings relevant to Early Medieval North West England (for GIS data, reference this article’s supplemental material at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11067607>).

Creation of optimal paths

A methodology was devised to create a network suite of probability-based optimal paths that depict varying densities of foot travel, with barriers to foot travel at major wetlands. The base logic of the model is the use of a Monte Carlo simulation to account for error in the creation of the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) (*cf.* Lewis 2021), multiple costs of movement functions to simulate human agency as slope is encountered, and the use of magnitude-per-unit area calculations to describe line density (*figure 8*). The model was weighted to preference sections of digitized Romano-British roads derived from recent work by Bishop (2014) and Ratledge (2023), such as the re-discovered fragments of the Lancaster-Kendal route (Ratledge 2023). Five model simulations were completed to accommodate the available computing resources required to simulate random errors inherent in DEM creation. Vehicle transport was not chosen as a model parameter, as Edmonds (2020) considered foot and horse travel as the most likely trans-Pennine crossing methods. Foot travel here is estimated as a proxy for horse-bound travel between known segments of Romano-British roads. Foot travel in this model is again preferred to travel on navigable waterways, as navigable waterways did not traverse the Pennines and were considerably slower than terrestrial travel (Edmonds 2020).

Figure 8 – The optimal paths modelling workflow. Paths formed from the cost of vertical movement according to *Equations* (1), (2), and (3) across all iterations ($n = 5$) are combined into an overall suite of optimal pathways. The suite of optimal pathways is converted into a line density raster according to *Equation* (4).

Costs of horizontal and vertical movement

For foot travel on a Romano-British road course, a factor of 1.0 was applied to reflect the suggested cost factor for blacktop roads (Herzog 2014). For travel off Romano-British road courses, a factor of 1.1 was applied, the suggested factor for grass (*Ibid.* 2014). These factors were rasterized across the study area for application as the cost of horizontal movement in the model. Additional cost factors, such as those for heavy brush, ploughed fields, and loose sand may be appropriate in future study, but at this stage, fine-grained understanding of past land use in the study area is not known. Wetlands also play a part in defining possible areas of movement. While major wetlands would not have ultimately been barrier for movement for maritime societies of the Viking Age, major land routes would likely have diverted around marsh bogs for ease of travel purposes. For example, the Ramsar-designated wetland near the Silverdale and Arnside Area of Outstanding Beauty (AONB) was drained in the early modern period and would likely have been a barrier to foot travel in the early medieval period. Romano-British and early medieval routeways known in this area divert around this wetland, rather than attempting a crossing by boat. To approximate past wetlands in the absence of geoarchaeologically-delineated wetland evidence across the study area, Ramsar Wetlands of International Importance in England were used in the model as barriers to horizontal movement. Recent wetland prediction models, such as the Wetland Identification Model (O’Neil *et al.* 2020) hold much potential for the delineation of past wetlands, but remain unproven for archaeological study. Therefore, Ramsar wetlands were applied in raster format, derived from a base dataset (Natural England, 2021) in shapefile format. Other possible barriers to movement, such as a lack of maintenance on sections of road in the tenth century, are possible but at present unknown in specific locations.

Three functions that describe the costs of vertical movement with respect to slope were used in the model. These three functions are standard and common options to describe slope-dependent costs of horizontal movement (*cf.* Herzog 2010, 2014, Lewis 2021), and were used to create rasterized line densities describing the costs of horizontal movement. Three functions were selected because of limits on available Random Access Memory (RAM) computing capabilities within ArcGIS Pro 3.0. Future studies may implement more or all common cost functions to create rasterized optimal path line densities, such

as those described in Herzog (2014) or Lewis (2021). The first equation used in this model is the classic Tobler's (1993) hiking function, given as *Equation (1)*.

$$(1) \quad V(s) = 6 * \exp(-3.5 * \text{abs}(s+0.05))$$

The second equation used was the modified version of Tobler's hiking function described in Márquez-Pérez *et al.* (2017), given as *Equation (2)*.

$$(2) \quad V(s) = 4.8 * \exp(-5.3 * \text{abs}((s*0.7)+0.03))$$

The third equation used to describe the cost of vertical movement was the sixth-degree polynomial following Minetti *et al.* (2002) and Herzog (2010), given below as *Equation (3)*.

$$(3) \quad \text{Cost}(s) = 1337.8 s^6 + 278.19 s^5 - 517.39 s^4 - 78.199 s^3 + 93.419 s^2 + 19.825 s + 1.64$$

Model iteration process

To iterate multiple equally-possible outcomes in the LCP creation process, a custom Monte Carlo simulation was created in a Jupyter notebook for ArcGIS Pro 3.0. It is recognized that the standard errors inherent in the DEM creation process have the potential to change modelling outcomes, particularly in the case of viewshed studies (Fisher 1993) and LCP studies (Lewis 2021). Monte Carlo simulation is a common method of describing multiple outcomes in the modelling process (Fischer 1993, Lewis 2021) and is used here to address multiple equally probable outcomes in LCP creation. The base DEM used for this model was the United Kingdom Ordnance Survey Terrain-50 DEM product, a 50m resolution elevation raster which has a standard error of $\pm 4\text{m}$ (Ordnance Survey, 2022). The model was automated in the Jupyter notebook with multiple iterations. For each iteration, the base DEM was combined with a second DEM consisting of solely random errors according to the base DEM's standard deviation (*cf.* Lewis 2021). One optimal path per route pairing was created for each of the three employed cost functions, using the 'Distance Accumulation' (ESRI 2023) and 'Optimal Path as Line' (ESRI 2023) tools. The Distance Accumulation tool utilizes Sethian's (1999) interpretation of the Eikonal Equation to compute geodesic paths across surfaces. Across five iterations of the Monte Carlo simulation, fifteen optimal paths were created per route pairing.

The steps performed by the iterating process to create the optimal paths are as follows:

1. A base DEM (OS Terrain-50) of $\pm 4\text{m}$ was interpolated to discrete point data and combined with random errors of to yield a new DEM with incorporated random errors.
2. The Surface Parameters Slope tool (ESRI 2023) was applied to the random errors DEM to calculate degrees of slope across the DEM.
3. The Surface Parameters Aspect tool (ESRI 2023) was applied to the random errors DEM to calculate the direction of downslope change in the DEM as a compass angle.
4. The on-path/off-path factors raster was given as the cost of horizontal movement.
5. The cost of vertical movement from each of *Equation (1,2,3)*, respectively, was implemented in a Vertical Factor (VF table) spreadsheet and used in alternating model runs. The VF table was computed outside GIS and inserted into the GIS as a .txt file. The VF table for each of *Equation (1,2,3)* uses the correspondent cost function to compute the cost of movement at a cell of a given slope.
6. One pathway between each set of early medieval period transport nodes was given for each cost function.

Conversion to rasterized line densities

The model outputs were stored as polyline features in a geodatabase and converted to line densities. The line densities displayed areas of highest-probability traffic flow following the Monte Carlo simulation of multiple cost of vertical movement functions. Line densities were computed as a raster with magnitude-per-unit area values using the Line Density tool (ESRI 2023) in ArcGIS Pro 3.0. The line densities were computed according to *Equation (4)*. The equation calculates for every cell the density of polyline features within a set neighborhood radius (*cf.* Silverman 1986),

$$(4) \quad \text{Density} = ((L1 * V1) + (L2 * V2)) / (\text{neighborhood radius})$$

where L1 and L2 are the lengths of portions of lines that lie within the neighborhood radius, and V1 and V2 are magnitude values. The neighborhood radius is the search area for LCPs that occur around a particular point in the map. The neighborhood radius needs to be sufficient to account for the width of possible two-dimensional variation in course of the optimal paths. Deng *et al.* (2014) highlight the arbitrary nature in selecting neighborhood search radii when estimating density of GIS features, and note that the neighborhood radius needs to be appropriate to the scale of the related features in a spatial distribution. For the LCPs depicted in the current study, no special weighting was added to the magnitude values of each line and each pathway must be considered equally due to the nature of the Monte Carlo simulation. A neighborhood radius of 100m is considered by the author to be appropriate for this study to capture all deviations in course between parallel LCPs between the same destinations and was used to create line densities depicted in this paper.

Validation of routes between destinations

Single finds from the PAS are typically recovered by metal detectorists and can be viewed as artefacts which have likely been accidentally lost by their owners, perhaps while travelling through the landscape (Kershaw 2017b). The distribution of PAS single finds is biased towards metal detecting tendencies, the availability of permission to detect in certain areas, and Romano-British road courses (Richards, Naylor, and Holas-Clarke 2009). However, the presence of single finds in an area can be viewed as positive indicators that activity took place within a landscape. All single finds on the PAS from the eighth to eleventh centuries were downloaded in order to test their distribution against the generated optimal paths. The positions of single finds in the study area are presented in the results as one means of model performance assessment.

Departure pathways modelling and validation of routeways

To analyze the relationship of the hoard depositional points to the generated optimal paths, departure paths from the main routes to the silver hoard locations were computed. The departure paths created in this process were designed to simulate off-route travel to the depositional locations, to simulate the walking time and potential pathways for a depositing or recovering agent to encounter hoard locations. Departure paths were simulated to reflect possible events that a hoard was deposited while in transit between destinations, or a previously-deposited hoard was encountered by an agent moving on a major route. To test this scenario, departure points were set at regular intervals of 100m along the highest optimal path densities at a perpendicular angle to the hoard locations. These departure points were used to calculate optimal paths using the same modelling process as above, from the areas of highest density to the hoard depositional points. Walking times in this analysis were estimated assuming an average walking speed of 1.4 meters per second. It is intended that depositional locations that are located away from routeways, such as those that required several minutes' walking time away from high-traffic areas of the landscape, may be considered 'concealed' deposits under this framework.

Results

Optimal Path Performance

The network suite of optimal paths largely mirrors the Romano-British roads on a regional scale (*figure 9*). However, in some instances, the optimal paths deviate from the Romano-British road courses (see discussion of *waingates* below). Many of the routes showed evidence for early medieval period use. In particular, routes from Aldborough to Ilkley, Ilkley to Preston, Penrith to Ingleton, Kendal to Barrow-in-Furness, and Broughbridge to Richmond showed positive evidence for use in the early medieval period. Furthermore, this analysis finds that the silver hoard depositional locations are placed with a median walking time of 16 minutes away from the routeways depicted in this model.

Figure 9 – The network suite of optimal paths.

Relationship of routeways to Single Finds

The Broughbridge-Ilkley Pennine crossing contained several single finds that were used to validate model performance (*figure 10*). This section is part of the broader York-Ribchester route, a route that may have gone out of use following the Romano-British period and been supplanted by other roughly-parallel paths of medieval date (Ratledge, *pers. comm.*). The optimal paths in this section support the assertion that the Romano-British route had gone out of use and been supplanted by a parallel route as many single finds are recorded along the optimal paths route. The first find that hints at the usage of a parallel track is a cast lead weight (PAS 'Find-ID' SWYOR-6F5978) of 22 grams that is thought to date from AD 850-1000, and has been compared to Hiberno-Norse weights of the same mass (Downes 2020). The second single find is a ninth century Carolingian copper-alloy brooch (SWYOR-906685) that may have arrived in England from Viking activity (Downes 2008). A c. AD 750-950 copper alloy Thomas Class A, Type 2 strap end (YORYM-2EE1EE) was recorded near the optimal paths. Interestingly, a group of single finds including early medieval gaming pieces, weights, and a fragmented Dirham from c. AD 750-950 (SWYOR-E07258) were found in close proximity to the optimal paths, slightly north of the Romano-British road line and the optimal paths. Finds of this nature are often indicative of Viking-Age trading sites or campsites and are observed to occur in places overlooking routeways (Hadley and Richards 2016). I do not suggest here that this distribution is a Viking-Age trading or camp site (as it consists of five finds) but that a precedent exists for explaining distributions of these types of finds near to, but slightly away from, tenth century routes and can be applied as a rule of thumb for understanding their overall distribution in relation to observed routes.

Figure 10 – Single finds on the Broughbridge-Ilkley Pennine crossing path.

In the Lancashire and Cumbrian routes, single finds were also closely associated with the model outputs. The optimal paths between the Ribble Valley and Ilkley contained six Viking Age single finds distributed within c. 500-meters from the points of highest density. These artefacts included two copper ingots (LANCUM-53BBB4, LANCUM-9CB512), a Swedish-Varangian style scabbard (LANCUM-692561), and a late tenth century Petersen Type X sword pommel (LANCUM-682DB1) (*figure 11*). On the north-south route that runs between Penrith and Ingleton, a gold Viking-type finger ring (LANCUM-ED5E96) was found that parallels forms from Ireland in the late ninth and early tenth centuries (Boughton 2008). Routes from Kendal to Barrow-in-Furness and Lancaster demonstrated positive evidence for stray object loss with both a Viking-import Irish stick pin (LANCUM-332D63) and a tenth or eleventh century quillion (LANCUM-F7D49D) recorded in the PAS.

Figure 11 – PAS Finds in the Ribble Valley. The east-west routes to Ilkley follow the same general path, but the north-south routes diverge. The distribution of single finds largely follows the distribution of optimal paths.

Comparison with documentary and placename evidence

The optimal paths in this model additionally performed well in Lancashire when compared to post-medieval documentary evidence. The antiquarian John Leland famously recorded the route taken northwards from Preston towards Lancaster (Leland, *ed.* Smith 1909). Leland gave particular mention to bridges and distances travelled. In c. 1540, Leland writes that he crossed the Savick Brook ‘one mile without Preston’. It is recorded by Ratledge (2023) that the Romano-British road that passes through Moor Park in Preston crosses another Romano-British road (modern Watling Street Road) near Savick Brook. This crossing point is presumably the crossing point that Leland used, as it sits nearly 0.95 miles north of the post-medieval boundary of Preston in the Moor Hall and Gallows Hill area. The optimal paths in this model performed well in this context, as the paths crossed Savick Brook at the same point as Leland in the sixteenth century.

Across the Pennines on routes from York, optimal paths across most iterations divert near the modern village of Rocliffe (Yorkshire), away from the small wetland at the River Tutt. Waingates Lane is located west of the small wetland in this location. A *waingate* is defined as a ‘wagon street’, a placename believed to date from c. 1700 originating from Yorkshire’s West Riding (Smith 1961). Here, the denoted ‘wagon street’ diverts c. 200-meters from the Romano-British road course and may be associated with poor drainage near the River Tutt. The modelled optimal paths reflect this local topography and placename by also diverting around the wetland (*figure 12*).

Figure 12 – Optimal paths and the Roecliffe waingate. The optimal paths pass 200m from Waingate Lane, Roecliffe, and a small wetland across the original road course.

Hoards' relationship to routeways

Areas of high-density early medieval period travel suggested by this modelling process are located up to *c.* 60 minutes' walk from the depositional points of Viking Age silver hoards in North West England (*table 3, figure 13*). A concentration of 11 hoards in the North West were located in the sub-25 minute travel time range. Furthermore, all hoards that are known to have been deposited with containers ($n = 5$) were located in the sub-25 minute travel time range.

	Name	County	Category	Deposition Date Range (AD)	Container	Off-path travel time (minutes)	Related Route
1	Cuerdale	Lancashire	Mixed	905-910	Lead	20.6	Preston-Ribchester
2	Huxley	Cheshire	Bullion	900-910	Lead	10.1	Chester-Repton
3	Silverdale	Lancashire	Mixed	900-910	Lead	5.9	Lancaster-Kendal
4	Harkirk	Lancashire	Mixed	910-915		16.0	Wigan
5	Dean	Cumbria	Coin	915-925	Lead	16.1	Ravenglass-Cockermouth
6	Lancashire	Lancashire	Coin	910-920			
7	Chester (St. John)	Cheshire	Coin	915-920		0.5	Chester
8	Warton/Carnforth	Lancashire	Mixed	920-929		10.4	Lancaster-Kendal
9	Flusco Pike (2)	Cumbria	Mixed	920-929		32.0	Penrith-Ingleton

10	Scotby	Cumbria	Mixed	935-940		60.9	
11	Flusco Pike (1)	Cumbria	Ornament	920-939		29.6	Penrith- Ingleton
12	Orton Scar	Cumbria	Ornament			37.0	Penrith- Ingleton
13	Eccleston	Cheshire	Bullion			10.5	Carlisle- Penrith
14	Barrow-in-Furness	Cumbria	Mixed	900-930		46.8	Barrow- Kendal
15	Chester (Castle Esplanade)	Cheshire	Mixed	965-970	Pot	4.0	Chester
16	Halton Moor	Lancashire	Mixed	1025-1030	Silver Cup	16.2	Lancaster- Ingleton
17	West Coast Cumbria	Cumbria	Mixed	850-950		55.2	Ravenglass- Cockermouth
18	Furness	Cumbria	Mixed	955-957		17.6	Barrow- Kendal

Table 3 – Approximate off-path travel times from the optimal paths to the hoard locations, given in minutes.

Figure 13 – The distribution of approximate off-path travel time in minutes. The range of approximate off-path travel times was up to c. 60 minutes' walk from the nearest points of highest density in the optimal path network. The median off path travel time is 16.0 minutes. There is a concentration of 11 hoards that are located in the sub-25 minute walking time zone.

Hoards related to cross-Pennine routes were the Cuerdale, Halton Moor, Scotby, both Chester hoards, and both Flusco Pike hoards. The Scotby Hoard is related to routes at the Tyne Gap. The Flusco Pike hoards are related to routes in the Eden Valley. The Cuerdale Hoard is related to routes in the Pennine Dales Fringe and Lancashire Valleys. The Chester hoards are related to routes through the Southern Pennines (all *table 3*).

Hoards related to North-South travel along the west coast of Lancashire are Silverdale, Wharton/Carnforth, and Halton Moor. Hoards related to the West Cumbria Coastal Plain North-South routes are the Dean and West Coast Cumbria Hoards. The Huxley and Eccleston hoards are likely related to travel south from Cumbria (all *table 3*).

Discussion

Concealed deposits

Debates have prevailed in Viking Age hoarding studies as to the ritual or non-ritual status of individual hoards. It has been suggested by Gruszczynski (2017) that Viking Age coin hoards in Scandinavia can be viewed as ritual in nature if they are deposited in areas that are impossible to retrieve, and several authors (Raffield 2014, Bradley 2017, Gruszczynski 2017) suggest that wetlands are a location frequented for ritual deposition of objects in the Viking Age. However, Bradley (2017) states that it is difficult to discern the wetland status of hoards. None of the hoards in the North West were located in Ramsar-designated wetlands (*figure 14*). Although further study of the relationship of the hoards to wetlands can be undertaken, preliminary indications from this study are that the hoards conform to a non-wetland depositional context.

Figure 14 – The distribution of silver hoards and Ramsar wetlands around the Morecambe Bay. The hoards lay in well-drained positions away from the large wetlands. Some hoards are located over 20km from the nearest wetland. The roads model includes Ratledge’s revised Lancaster-Kendal line (2023).

Further clues to the non-ritual status of the hoards in this analysis are the presence of containers and economically-valuable objects. Gruszczynski (2017) suggested that containers indicate that hoards are intended to be retrieved. Six of the hoards in the North West were buried with containers, and the presence of organic containers in the other cases cannot be ruled out due to soil preservation conditions. Bradley (2017) suggests that Viking Age hoards are non-ritual in nature if they contain artefacts of whole or fragmentary nature. Bradley’s implication is that the hoards are intended to be retrieved if they

contain objects that will be of future economic or practical use to the owner. All of the hoards in North West England are composed of objects that were of current economic value at the time of their deposition.

If hoards are ritually-deposited if they are placed in areas that are impossible to retrieve (Gruszczynski 2017), the hoards in the North West are by implication non-ritual deposits, as they were deposited in areas that were highly-retrievable within short walking distances of major routes. Based on an analysis of its material composition, it is possible that the Cuerdale Hoard was in transit from York (Williams 2011) or assembled in the Ribble Valley, a central meeting place between York and Dublin (Graham-Campbell 2011). However, both authors imply transportation of the hoard immediately prior to deposition. The deposit location is on a dry rise near the riverbank – the hoard was only discovered when the decision was made to construct a wider river channel and bank in 1840. The depositional location was on the opposite side of the bank from the east-west Romano-British road leading away from Preston towards Pennine crossings past the Lancashire valleys. The hoard was located approximately two kilometers from the Roman bridge at Walton-le-Dale and one kilometer from the river crossings indicated by the optimal paths model (figure 15). Thus, if elements of the hoard from Ireland arrived by ship, the depositors likely would have sailed between one and two kilometers past popular Ribble crossing locations before choosing a location to bury the hoard. If elements of the hoard arrived by land, the depositors may have left popular land routes for some one to two and a half kilometers. Measured in minutes' walking time, the results of this project indicate that the Cuerdale Hoard may have been deposited approximately 20 minutes' walking time from high-traffic pathways. Future work must be undertaken to analyze the visibility of the hoard findspot from major routeways and the deepest channels of the Ribble, but preliminary indications in this study are that the findspot is away from major routes.

Figure 15 – The relationship of off-path routes to the Cuerdale Hoard. The intersection of routes in the Preston area is c. 2.5 km away from the hoard deposit. To encounter the hoard location, the Ribble would have needed to be forded in most scenarios, as shown with the departure path densities.

Similarly, another case study is the second Flusco Pike hoard (*figure 16*), buried approximately 1.5-2.5km from the optimal paths' highest density segments through the modern Penrith vicinity. The indicated walking times from high-density areas lends an estimate of approximately 30 minutes. The hoard, similarly to Cuerdale, was placed away from the location of the optimal pathways between major transport nodes.

Figure 16 –The relationship of off-path routes to the second (most recently-discovered) hoard in the Flusco Pike/Penrith area.

In all instances, the hoards were buried up to one hour's walking time away from high-traffic areas of the landscape, with a concentration of deposits in the under-25 minute category. The hoards were likely intended to be retrieved due to economically valuable components deposited together in a container in several instances, with further non-ritual indications coming from the doubtful wetland status of the deposits addressed. The summation of the elements discussed here depicts a framework where the hoard depositors chose locations away from high-traffic routes, as the economically valuable hoard components were likely transported on those routes from their various origin points to their final depositional location. Furthermore, the depositors may have chosen locations that were peripheral to high-density traffic flow to assist in their concealment from others on the routes, and to ensure the safekeeping of the deposit in anticipation of the owners' return.

Conclusion

Viking Age silver hoards in the North West are often viewed as being deposited in an intermediary landscape between York and Dublin. However, the nature of the relationship between specific courses of routeways and depositional points was unclear, leaving unresolved questions in the scholarship related to why certain locations were chosen to bury Scandinavian-economic character silver hoards in the study area. Furthermore, this research gap has allowed debates to persist on the hoards' relationship to overland transit and the intent of the depositors to return for the hoards. To move towards resolving these debates, optimal pathways were implemented that took into account re-discovered Romano-British road segments, uncertainty in DEM production, and the agency of multiple walkers in the landscape via multiple cost of vertical movement equations.

This study has targeted two specific previously-understudied research questions relating to the silver hoards as discussed in the introduction. Firstly, this study set out to examine the relationship of the hoards to their routeways. It was shown that the hoards' depositional points are related to early medieval communications routes between Northumbria and the Irish Sea region. The links between Northumbria and the Irish Sea are significant as they were the locations two hubs of Scandinavian influence in the area – the 'linked kingdoms' of York and Dublin, which were sources of Viking bands operating on the western shores of England in the early tenth century and the apparent influx of Scandinavian settlers in the North West at this time. Secondly, this study set out to test if the hoards were concealed deposits intended for retrieval. It was shown that further to the hoards being related to the early medieval period routes, the hoards were buried up to one hour's walk from the routes, with a median walking time of 16 minutes. Eleven of the hoards in the study were located within a sub-25 minute walking time. Taken together with the presence of other non-ritual elements, such as containers in some instances, the hoards are viewed as a group of similar deposits that were concealed from routeways and intended by their depositors to be retrieved.

Future Research

To further this hypothesis of seclusion from routes, GIS-based visibility analysis of the routes and silver hoard locations will likely prove profitable. Visibility analysis may take the form of a traditional viewshed analysis from locations along routes, similar to the locational analysis proposed by Eve and Crema (2014), or may take the form of a seclusion or covert space analysis as proposed by Gillings (2016). Furthermore, a structuring of node importance will improve the understanding of the network's relationship to hoard locations, and a working model of node structuring can be derived from processes inspired by Brooks and Nguyen Huynh (2018). It is hoped that the summation of these analyses applied to hoard locations will continue to contribute to the understanding of depositional landscapes. The inclusion of LiDAR data in substitution for the Terrain-50 DEM may yield further granularity to the analysis presented here, and may assist in wetland analysis at a large scale. Finally, the method presented in this paper will be of interest to those studying hoards of other periods and geographic regions, and it is hoped that it will be useful in contexts other than the study of Early Medieval Britain.

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Conflict of interest disclosure

The author has no conflicts of interest, financial or otherwise, in relation to the content of the article, in compliance with the rules set out by PCI.

Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

The grid coordinates of artefacts recorded through the Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS) are restricted to users with Research-level access, subject to Crown Copyright and the conditions, responsibilities, and stipulations of the 1996 Treasure Act of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland. Therefore, the grid coordinates of specific artefacts registered with the PAS discussed in this article are not publicly available. Similarly, some silver hoards are registered with county Historic Environment Record (HER) offices in England. Permission to use these coordinates for academic study must be obtained directly from the relevant HER offices.

Python scripts used to perform the optimal pathways modelling depicted in this paper are available in .ipynb format at Wilcox, Wyatt. (2024). Mobility and the reuse of Roman Roads for the deposition of Viking Age silver hoards in North West England (Supplemental Material) (Version 1). CAA 2023 Amsterdam: 50 Years of Synergy, Amsterdam, Netherlands. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11067607>. This Supplemental Material link also includes the optimal paths between nodes depicted in the paper in both line and raster format, a nodes feature class, and VF tables used in the analysis.

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